

Project number: 730879

Project acronym: INFRAFRONTIER2020

Project title: Development of mouse mutant resources for functional analyses of human diseases - Enhancing the translation of research into innovation

D5.2 Production of 22 Genome-Edited Mouse Models

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Table of contents:

Introduction1

Call Overview1

Selected User Projects4

Outcomes..... 11

Hidden costs and Problems 16

Outlook..... 16

 Stand-alone dedicated INFRAFRONTIER service.....16

Application Form 17

Introduction

This report compiles information about the precision mouse models trans-national access (TNA) calls i.e., call overview, selected user projects, outcomes and outlook.

The main service providers involved were:

- Biological Sciences Research Center A. Fleming (BSRC)
- Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (CNB-CSIC).
- Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI).
- Genome Research Limited (Sanger).

The infrastructure required for conducting this TNA call was provided by four independent INFRAFRONTIER nodes offering this service routinely to researchers of their institutions, to external clients and / or as partners in large collaborative research projects such as the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC). They are equipped with up-to-date tools and have access to animal facilities where genetically modified animals are housed in specific units, their use is registered and reported to authorities and inspections are performed on a regular basis. They have proven capability to produce genetically modified animals using a variety of approaches such as ES cell injections and have adopted new gene editing technologies such as CRISPR/Cas9. All partners have specialized personnel with the required expertise to produce genetically modified animals using state-of-art technologies. All production units are associated with the corresponding archiving facilities at each centre. This allows the cryopreservation of all new mouse created by the Trans-national Access service and ensures access to the wider scientific community.

Call Overview

Two calls for mouse precision models were launched in November 2017 and January 2019. In the second reporting period, three WP5 calls were successfully executed. The call information and documents related to WP5 can be accessed at:
<https://www.infrafrontier.eu/resources-and-services/infrafrontier-open-calls>.

The call scope of both the mouse modelling services was described in the call documents as follows:

Main objective of this INFRAFRONTIER open call is to facilitate access for the wider biomedical research community to the unique infrastructure and scientific expertise of the participating INFRAFRONTIER partners, to deliver novel mouse lines that will advance knowledge of human disease and will be of widespread use in biomedical science. Recent advances in genome editing technology will be used to develop new mouse models of human disease. INFRAFRONTIER will provide open access to all newly developed disease models through the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA). Access to this free-of-charge-service will be granted on the basis of the applicant's research plans and the potential impact of the proposed novel mouse line on the wider biomedical research community.

A total of 47 mouse proposals were submitted and 22 accepted into the production pipelines.

The access unit covered the production of a single F1 genome-edited mouse line (at least one individual of a F1 genome edited mouse line would be provided). The model development involved project design, preparation of CRISPR-Cas9 reagents, and injection into or electroporation of mouse zygotes to generate F0 founder genome-edited animals in C57BL/6J or C57BL/6N, genetic backgrounds, respectively. Selected F0 animals were bred to produce F1 animals. All generated mouse models were planned to be made available to the scientific community and deposited into the INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA archive.

Proposals were submitted from 16 different countries, including submissions from US, Canada and South Africa. The review was based on short descriptions of the projects involving the mouse mutants that will be produced by the TA service. A mixed panel of members of INFRAFRONTIER and of an external Evaluation Committee assessed service requests supported by the TA activity. In addition to scientific merit of applicants, soundness of the proposal and research plans, and the beneficial impact of the proposed novel mouse line on the wider biomedical research community was evaluated. Applicants were informed on the outcome of the evaluation within 6 weeks after the end of the call. All applications were handled with strict confidentiality.

Geographic origin of submitted WP5 proposals

TA call website:

Call 1: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/resources-and-services/infrafrontier-open-calls/precision-mammalian-model-development>

Call 2: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/resources-and-services/infrafrontier-open-calls/precision-mammalian-model-development-mouse-models>

Total number of applications: 47

Selected user projects: 22

Gender distribution: 68% male; 32% female

Research area / disease / syndrome covered in selected CRISPR/Cas9 production projects:

- Leukemogenesis
- Acute myeloid leukemia
- Chronic lymphocytic leukemias
- Wilms tumor
- BRCA2 tumor
- Colon cancer
- Lung adenocarcinoma
- Malignant hematopoiesis
- Neurofibromatosis type 1
- Hereditary CST3-related cerebral amyloid angiopathy
- Stroke
- Shwachman-Bodian-Diamond syndrome
- Charcot-Marie-Tooth neuropathy
- Neurological disorders
- Autism spectrum disorders
- Intellectual disability
- Pilarowski-Bjornsson syndrome
- Inherited retinal degeneration
- Thyroid disorders
- Systemic capillary leak syndrome
- Influenza A virus pathogenesis

18 CRISPR/Cas9 production projects re-engineer mutations identified in patients

Selected User Projects

Selected precision mouse model development projects from the first call

Production centre	Applicant	Gene of interest	Project scope
CNB-CSIC Partner 15	Goutebroze France	Cntnap2	CNTNAP2, a susceptibility gene for Autism Spectrum Disorders: genetic variations, background and environment. Project aims to provide a proof of principle that some CNTNAP2 variants may be pathogenic and to evaluate their interactions with genetic background and environmental factors in ASD.
BSRC Fleming Partner 6	Stamatopoulos Greece	Sf3b1	Induce a human mutation to the highly conserved mouse homologue of SF3B1 using CrispR/Cas9 technology. Generate mutant mice carrying the dominant variant SF3B1 (K700E) to understand how aberrant splicing offers competitive advantage and drives leukemogenesis.
NKI Partner 23	Nijink Canada	Mysm1	Testing the Role of MYSM1 Deubiquitinase Catalytic Activity in Transcriptional Regulation of Normal and Malignant Hematopoiesis. Requesting the production of a mouse line carrying point-mutant Mysm1D660N allele that renders MYSM1 protein catalytically inactive, to be produced on the C57BL/6N background.
BSRC Fleming Partner 6	Makris Greece	Rps15	Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemias (CLL) arise due to a combination of driver mutations. RPS15 identified in 20% of CLL patients relapsing after chemotherapy. Project aims to introduce the mutation RPS15 ^{P1315} into the mouse genome to develop a tool in the effort to understand the significance of these alterations to the onset of disease, cell homeostasis and role in stress signaling.
Sanger Institute Partner 28	Pilarowski Iceland	Chd1	Missense variants in CHD1 (chromatin remodeler) cause neurodevelopmental delay, hypotonia, and speech apraxia through a dominant negative mechanism. Therefore, loss of function variants would not be expected to lead to the disease phenotype. Project aim: Generation and validation of the first mouse model of Pilarowski-Bjornsson syndrome in order to establish genotype-phenotype causation and understand impact of specific patient missense mutations.

CNB-CSIC Partner 15	Primig France	Exosc10	Anti-cancer drug resistance is a serious problem for widely used 5-fluorouracil (5-FU)-based chemotherapies. We hypothesize that elevated levels of EXOSC10, a conserved exoribonuclease inhibited by 5-FU, promote cell proliferation and 5-FU resistance. Our objectives are to test if a point mutation identified in a colon cancer sample (RHS402>TLDHL) stabilizes EXOSC10 in vivo, and if increased EXOSC10 protein levels alter cell division and differentiation during embryogenesis and adult development.
NKI Partner 23	Mazur USA	Mettl21b	METTL21b is a potential critical regulator of tumorigenesis. It was identified as an oncogene and is often amplified in tumours, correlated with poor survival. Lung adenocarcinoma (LAC) is one of the deadliest and most aggressive forms of cancer. Most patients develop resistances to current cancer therapies which could be mediated by METTL21b. Therefore, loss of function Mettl21b mutations in mice variants would be informative to clarify its role in cancer. Project aim: Generation and validation of Mettl21b mouse knockout mutants through a deletion approach facilitated by CRISPR-Cas9.
BSRC Fleming Partner 6	Kostourou Greece	Talin1	Systemic capillary leak syndrome (SCLS) is a rare medical condition characterized by acute, life threatening episodes of increased capillary permeability, resulting in vascular collapse, plasma extravasation, edema and hypotensive shock. The aim of the project is to generate an in vivo model of SCLS by mimicking the Talin1 mutation found in patients of SCLS, in order to unravel the pathophysiology of this disease, and to gain further insight into the molecular mechanisms of how Talin1 mutations drive this.
Sanger Partner 28	Demassy France	Cxxc1	The project aims to decipher molecular mechanisms responsible for meiotic recombination in mice. CXX1 plays an essential role for mediating protein-protein interactions of PRDM9, SPO11 and IHO1. The CRISPR model development project will delete a conserved motif (CPEH, 553-556) in the PHD2 domain of CXX1 responsible for IHO1 interaction. The homozygous mutant mice (CXXC1 DCPEH/DCPEH) are predicted to be viable and to only have meiotic defects.

Sanger Partner 28	Mosialos Greece	Spata2l	CRISPR/Cas mediated targeting of the Spata2l locus will be performed in order to generate a deletion of exon 2. Mice homozygous for this deletion (Spata2lD2/D2) will be examined for signs of spontaneous inflammation. In addition Spata2lD2/D2 MEFs will be isolated and tested for their response to TNF and LPS by examining their viability, NF-kappaB activating potential and NF-kappaB-target gene expression. Spata2lD2/D2 mice will be also bred to Spata2-deficient mice in order to determine whether the two molecules have overlapping functions. These studies will uncover the biological role of two recently identified regulators of innate immune signaling and they have the potential to uncover novel regulatory mechanisms of inflammatory responses and potential targets for pharmacologic interventions.
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Selected precision mouse model development projects from the second call

Production centre	Applicant	Gene of interest	Project scope
BSRC Fleming Partner 6	Laporte France, IGBMC, Strasbourg	Myotubularin* (MTM1)	Characterise the behavior, histological and molecular phenotypes of Mtm1C375S/y mice compared to control WT littermates. Based on data on other mouse models previously phenotyped in the same tests, 9 mice per group will be used. Once the line is established by Infrafrontier, application to ethical committee for animal experimentation will be performed. Phenotyping will be performed at IGBMC-ICS in Illkirch-France, ICS is part of PHENOMIN and Infrafrontier, and will include motor activity and coordination (actimeter, rotarod, string test, hanging test, cat walk for automated gait analysis), isolated muscle force with a force transducer (Aurora Scientific), histology of fast, mixed and slow muscles (Tibialis anterior, Gastrocnemius, Soleus, respectively), and molecular characterization as level and subcellular localization of the mutated MTM1 protein in skeletal muscles. All materials for phenotyping are available in-house and was previously used by the applicant's team on other mouse models. Importantly, the applicant has recently validated several rescuing approaches in the Mtm1 KO model. Assuming the phosphatase-dead Mtm1C375S/y mouse displays a muscle phenotype, these therapeutic approaches will be tested, especially trying to re-balance the level of

			phospholipids by inhibition of a PI 3-kinase. To this end, a kinase-dead mouse for the PI 3-kinase C2 β from B Vanhaesebroeck has been obtained.
Sanger Institute Partner 28	Gabriel Germany, Leibniz Institute for Experimental Virology, Hamburg	KPNA6 (Importin- alpha7)	Importin- α 7 appears to be a key factor in mediating Influenza A virus pathogenesis in mice and most likely in humans. The applicants showed that genetic polymorphisms in the importin- α 7 gene could indeed modulate its function, which not only affect IAV replicative fitness but also alter its ability to interact with components of major cellular machineries. This could lead to disturbed nuclear transport, altered cellular homeostasis and ultimately human disease. Within the proposal the aim is to generate a CRISPR-Cas9 mouse line that carries a polymorphism at position 162 (I162M, isoleucine exchanged for methionine) in the murine importin- α 7 gene. The model will be used i) to investigate the pathogenesis of various IAV subtypes and ii) to further explore whether this particular polymorphism would affect essential cellular processes including transcription, gene regulation, and cell cycle progression.
CNB-CSIC Partner 15	Hohenstein Netherlands, Leiden University Medical Center, Leiden	Six1	Wilms tumours are pediatric kidney cancers that affect 1:10,000 children. As the tumour-initiating events that ultimately lead to Wilms' tumour formation occur long before birth of the (future) patient, for studying these early events genetically modified mouse models are indispensable. For a long time, <i>WT1</i> was one of only a few Wilms tumour genes that were known, but recently whole exome and genome sequencing efforts have identified many new Wilms' tumour genes, including <i>SIX1</i> . The <i>SIX1</i> Q177R mutation is a recurring somatic mutation found in unrelated patients. The combination of a clinically-relevant phenotype with relevance for normal kidney development and unique molecular effects makes <i>SIX1</i> Q177R an ideal mutation to be recapitulated using CRISPR/Cas9 in mice.
NKI Partner 23	Pettitt UK, Institute of Cancer Research, London	Brca2	Generation of a revertible mouse model of Brca2 loss: Knockout mouse models of Brca2 implicated BRCA2 as a regulator of DNA repair via homologous recombination (HR), and informed treatment studies of BRCA2 tumours with platinum salts or poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) inhibitors. Several drugs from these classes are now in clinical use for the treatment of breast and ovarian cancers with HR defects. However, acquired resistance to these agents is a growing clinical problem. The most common molecular mechanism of acquired clinical resistance to these agents

			appears to be secondary mutation (“reversion”) of the defective HR gene (i.e. BRCA2). Current conditional models and mouse tumours with e.g. acquired PARP inhibitor resistance may not mirror the most common clinical cause of resistance in humans. The applicant proposes to make a model of the BRCA2:c.6174delT allele in mice that has the capacity to revert, thus allowing a better modelling of the clinical disease.
BSRC Fleming Partner 6	Pujol Spain, ICREA / IDIBELL, Barcelona	SVBP	A mouse model for deciphering the role of Small Vasohibin Binding Protein (SVBP) in the brain and for finding therapies for a novel neurological disorder: Within a massive Spanish sequencing effort the applicant identified 5 subjects from 2 different families from the Basque country, harboring a homozygous missense variant in the SVBP gene. These patients present a childhood onset, symmetrical lower limb spastic paraplegia associated with cognitive delay and intellectual disability (data confirmed from two independent families) identifying SVBP as a novel gene crucial for brain development and function. For this reason, the applicants want to obtain Svbp ^{-/-} mice (null through CRISPR/Cas9). The new mouse model will allow to gain insight into the role of SVBP in these processes that affect homeostasis of tubulin tyrosination and detyrosination, particularly in the development and maintenance of the nervous system in vivo, in cell-autonomous and non-autonomous manner, and also allow for single-cell analysis. Importantly, the mouse model will be suitable to uncover therapeutic targets to ameliorate the expected neurological phenotype, which will be translated to preclinical test, and if successful, to clinical trials for these patients.
Sanger Institute Partner 28	Petit France, INSERM IRSET, Rennes	COUP-TFII or NR2F2	COUP-TFII (Chicken Ovalbumin Upstream Promoter - Transcription factor II or NR2F2): Although there is now evidence of a regulation of Coup-tfII expression by Hedgehog (Hh) in uterus, the precise mechanism of Coup-tfII expression during development, differentiation and homeostasis processes remains unclear. Deciphering the non-canonical hedgehog-PP2A-COUP-TFII pathway by analyzing the effect of a point mutation in a hedgehog responsive element of the Coup-tfII gene promoter should yield new insights on how and in which tissue Coup-tfII is regulated by this element. Specifically, the proposed project aims to delineate the function of the Shh Response Element in a new mouse model (Coup-tfII Δ ShhRE/ Δ ShhRE mouse line). The final goal is to provide new strategies in targeting the Hedgehog/COUP-TFII pathway for fertility and cancer therapies.
CNB-CSIC Partner 15	Kero Finland, University of Turku	TSHR	Thyroid disorders (hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism and thyroid tumors) are common diseases affecting more than 200 million people worldwide. The applicant's group has previously generated different genetically modified disease models to mimic human thyroid diseases. In the proposed project they suggest the production of mutant mice carrying a patient-derived (identified from several hyperthyroid

			patients) constitutively active thyroid-stimulating hormone receptor (TSHR) mutation shown to activate only the Gs- signalling pathway (TSHR M453T knock-in mutant).
Sanger Partner 28	Leveillard France, Sorbonne University, Paris	Nxn1	Inherited retinal degenerations are a group of diseases that alter the perception of light by photoreceptors of the retina. The most frequent, retinitis pigmentosa (RP), affects 2 million people worldwide. The applicant proposes to construct the poorcone (Nxn1PC/PC) mouse with a mutation in the NRE (nucleoredoxin-like 1 responsive element) using CRISPR/Cas9-mediated genome editing (Nucleolin (NCL) binds specifically to the NRE but not the mutated NRE). Objective is to test for the effect on cone function of the suppression of the metabolic signaling between rods and cones mediated by RdCVF (rod-derived cone viability factor). The rationale relies on the applicant's study of the mechanisms of production of the rod-derived cone viability factor (RdCVF) by alternative splicing of the nucleoredoxin-like 1 (NXNL1) gene by rods. The Nxn1PC/PC mice will be treated by delivery of RdCVF through an AAV to validate that the stimulation of the metabolic signaling using RdCVF in an animal for which the rod to cone signaling has been disrupted, leading to cone outer segment shortening, can promote the regrowth of the cone outer segment, restoring vision in a blind animal.
NKI Partner 23	Bozzi Italy, University of Trento	PTEN	Tensin Homolog Deleted on Chromosome Ten (PTEN) mutations and roles in autism spectrum disorder. Germline PTEN mutations have been characterized as the underlying cause of a number of tumor-susceptibility syndromes referred to as "PTEN hamartoma tumor syndromes" (PHTS) including Cowden disease (CD). Generally, the vast majority of PHTS/cancer associated PTEN mutations lose PTEN ability to control PI3K oncogenic pathway, while a high percentage of ASD associated PTEN mutations preserve this ability and their pathological roles remain elusive. Thus, the characterization of such mutant forms of PTEN will be of paramount relevance in order to define deregulated mechanisms and, in turn, tailored therapeutic strategies for ASD patients bearing PI3K-independent PTEN mutations. The applicant proposes to study a specific PTEN mutation related to ASD (C>A T167D, located in the phosphatase domain), whose pathological function, although unrelated to PI3K signaling, remains unknown. Mutant PTEN T167D knock-in (KI) mice will be studied to identify molecular, anatomical and behavioural phenotypes relevant to ASD.

CNB-CSIC Partner 15	Kreienkamp Germany, University Medical Center, Hamburg- Eppendorf	Dhx30	The applicant identified by trio-WES six different de novo missense mutations in DHX30 in twelve unrelated individuals affected by a severe form of global developmental delay and intellectual disability . DHX30 belongs to the DExH family of RNA helicases (RHs). The most common mutation was the Arg785Cys, identified in 4 independent patients. The proposed project aims to generate a mouse line carrying this specific mutation. Conventional Dhx30 ko mice do not survive beyond embryonic day 9.5 and are therefore not suitable for the intended studies. The applicant aims to provide a better understanding of the cellular and molecular consequences of the identified mutations and to delineate the role of DHX30 in brain development.
NKI Partner 23	Maharry USA, Ohio State University Cancer Center	Ccnd3	Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a heterogeneous disease that is characterized by the uncontrolled proliferation of myeloid blasts in the bone marrow. Despite significant advances in the treatment of AML patients over the last several decades, the outcomes of AML patients remain poor. One subset of AML with particularly poor outcome is AMLs involving translocations with the mixed-lineage leukemia (MLL) gene, affecting about 10% of all leukemia patients. Notably, the translocation cannot cause leukemia by itself, but requires a second hit event. Sequencing efforts by different groups recently discovered mutations in the gene cyclindependent kinase 3 (CCND3) as a recurrent event in MLL-translocated leukemias. The applicants are proposing the development of a Ccnd3 Thr261fs CRISPR model for the following specific aims: 1) Phenotyping of Ccnd3 Thr261fs homozygous mice. This may be of high importance not only for AML, but also other cancers involving recurrent CCND3 mutations, including Burkitt lymphoma, and 2) The Ccnd3 Thr261fs -t(11;19) mice will be used for testing of different CDK inhibitors.
BSRC Fleming Partner 6	Skoulakis Greece, BSRC Fleming, Vari	Nf1	Neurofibromatosis type 1 (NF1) is an autosomal dominantly inherited syndrome that affects 1:3000 individuals worldwide. It results from loss-of-function mutations of the neurofibromin (NF1) gene. While the tumor suppressor role of NF1 is well known, NF1 is a chronic multi-system disorder whose non-tumor symptoms contribute significantly to its morbidity. These include pigmentary lesions, vascular, skeletal abnormalities, and cognitive deficits. Currently there is no effective therapy for any NF1 symptom.

			It is estimated that the point mutations in NF1 gene are responsible for approximately 90% of cases of NF1 patients. This strongly indicates the necessity to generate and study animal models bearing mutations that mimic known human NF1 point mutations. The applicants propose to generate a mouse strain bearing the Arg1809Cys germline NF1 gene mutation to mimic one of the established human point mutations associated with cognitive deficits but not tumors. This will be a unique strain because to their knowledge, it will be the first Nf1 mutant mouse with a point mutation modelled after its equivalent in patients, and the first to test the functionality of this rather understudied domain of the Nf1 protein.
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* - Project was exchanged after notification from the user that it would be a duplication of effort. The user submitted a replacement project that was re-evaluated by the mixed Evaluation Committee and selected for the TA call (See Annex).

Outcomes

Researcher Name	User Project	Service Provider	Status	Remarks
Aurora Pujol	Svbp	BSRC	Completed / Ready for delivery	No response from user
Jocelyne Laporte	Mtm1	BSRC	Completed	This replaced Dnm2 project as this model was already generated
Efthimios Skoulakis	Nf1	BSRC	Completed	
Vassiliki Kostourou	Talin1	BSRC	Completed	
Kostas Stamatopoulos	Sf3b1	BSRC	Cancelled	Unsuccessful after several attempts and troubleshooting
Antonios Makris	Rps15	BSRC	Cancelled	Lethal
Laurence Goutebroze	Cntnap2	CNB	Completed	
Jukka Kero	Tshr	CNB	Completed	

Michael Primig	Exosc10	CNB	Cancelled	Lethal
Peter Hohenstein	Six1	CNB	Cancelled	Lethal
Hans Jürgen Kreienkamp	Dhx30	CNB	Cancelled	Lethal
Sophia Maharry	Ccnd3	NKI	Cancelled	Unsuccessful after several attempts and troubleshooting
Yuri Bozzi	PTEN	NKI	Ongoing	
Pawel Mazur	Mettl21b	NKI	Completed	
Anastasia Nijink	Mysm1	NKI	Completed	
Stephen Pettitt	Brca2	NKI	Completed	
Guelsah Gabriel	Kpna6	SANG	Completed	
Fabrice Petit	COUP-TFII	SANG	Completed	
Genay Pilarowski	Chd1	SANG	Completed	
George Mosialos	Spata2l	SANG	Cancelled	Offered and declined
Bernard De Massy	Cxxc1	SANG	Cancelled	Cancelled upon request by user: mutation could not be validated
Thierry Leveillard	Nxn1	SANG	Cancelled	Unsuccessful after several attempts and troubleshooting

User Feedback

User	Satisfied with the service	Willingness to pay a competitive price (non-profit) for the same service	Any publications being prepared	Feedback Remarks
Anastasia Nijnik	Yes	No	Not yet	
Stephen Pettitt	Yes	Maybe	Not yet	

Laurence Goutebroze	Yes	Maybe	Not yet	
Fabrice Petit	Yes	Maybe	Not yet	If you could include the transportation and the re-deriving of the mouse line, it would be great. Great experience and organization. Received an update (including all details of the procedure) once a month until the mouse line was generated.
Efthimios Skoulakis	Yes	Yes	Not yet	Highly enabling towards research directions difficult to have achieved without the relevant budget. Contributed significantly towards securing funding to followup.

Regarding Nxn1 project:

Explanation from the head of Molecular Technologies (Sanger Institute) team:

The challenge in generating this particular mutant allele is twofold; the CRISPR guide landscape in the immediate vicinity of the desired mutation site is limited and the mutation is large and complex putting pressure on the standard oligo donor approach.

*We observed non wildtype alleles in the F0s which were then bred to F1s in hope of transmitting the correct mutant allele, however when characterised the F1 hets are composed of a deletion allele and a mutant allele that is **not** the correct mutation. This could be either a result of guide disruption or partial oligo insertion. It would seem that an alternative approach will be required to achieve the desired mutation i.e., LssDNA donor/easiCRISPR*

Regarding Exosc10 project:

The service provider (CNB-CSIC) performed up to 8 genome editing microinjections and electroporations, involving 658 embryos and more than 30 transfers to foster females, only resulting in 9 surviving pups and none carrying the expected mutation but four carried various indels. It was later found out that Exosc10 mutation was lethal, as it had been reported by the same researcher a few years ago (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29118343/>). The user acknowledged this and wanted to use CRISPR-Cas9 via the TA call to get a surviving mouse mutant. This was a risky project with known lethality which not communicated in time.

Strategies employed for Ccnd3 and Pten projects:

Ccnd3

Were able to generate one correctly modified Ccnd3 founder that did not survive. Apart from this animal, several pups carrying indels were obtained.

Strategy 1: injection session 1 - 3 WT pups
injection session 2 - 23 pups (3 indels)

Strategy 2: different guide
injection session 3 - 2 WT pups
injection session 4 - 16 pups (1 with correct genotype, but died)
injection session 5 - 1 WT pup
injection session 6 - 3 pups (2 indels)
injection session 7 - 6 WT pups

Pten

For the Pten project, several pups carrying indels and one animal with the correct genotype were generated using different strategies. Upon breeding, this animal was not successful in generating offspring. Mating to superovulated females did not change this result. The animal was sacrificed, and sperm isolated and cryopreserved. IVF subsequently did not produce 2-cell stage embryos. As a last attempt, laser assisted

zona drilling procedures were used to facilitate sperm penetration. This experiment was very successful in terms of obtaining 2-cell embryo's; 6 fosters were transplanted. Pregnancies awaited.

- Strategy 1: 1 guide, HDR oligo
injection session 1 – 6 WT pups
- Strategy 2: 1 guide, 2x HDR oligo (mutant and WT = silent mutation)
injection session 2 – 19 pups (1 with silent mutation)
- Strategy 3: 2 guides, long ssDNA
injection session 3 – 13 pups (8 indels)
injection session 4 – 15 pups (1 with correct genotype)

Correct Pten founder breeding:

- no nests
- 2 females superovulated, 1 plugged, no pregnancies
- sperm freezing + IVF, no success, very few 2-cells

Hidden costs and Problems

The following issues were reported by the service providers:

- Validation of unexpected (and sometimes previously known/suspected) embryonic lethal alleles (useless repetition)
- Breeding and maintenance of colonies for researchers having difficulties to transfer the line to their laboratories
- Generating and shipping frozen sperm instead of mice for health status reasons
- Customers not interested in the model (offered and declined)
- Customers changing their mind on the model to be generated

These contributed to unanticipated hidden costs for the service providers.

Outlook

Out of the 22 user projects, 8 had to be cancelled due to the reasons mentioned above. Some user projects had to be cancelled because the generation of the mutants was very challenging, or the mutation was embryonic lethal. In some cases, this was already known by the users and the TA service was used for their validation. This was a waste of resources, time and money. One solution could be to have selected users declare any previous attempts or relevant information.

However, the user projects that were successfully completed and the unique mouse models generated thereof will be a valuable resource to the scientific community. These precision models can be used to study several diseases and disorders like influenza, autism spectrum disorders, breast and ovarian cancers, acute myeloid leukemia etc.

Stand-alone dedicated INFRAFRONTIER service

In a recent survey of TA call providers, BSRC have expressed interest in adapting this pilot TA call into an independent sustainable service outside of I2020 with a few changes. The service pricing will need reassessment and proposals need to be carefully evaluated on basis of embryonic lethality or duplication of effort. Other service providers like CNB-CSIC have also shown interest provided necessary fail safes are in place to prevent uptake of dead-end projects. Obtaining license agreements that will allow academic distribution of mice generated by the CRISPR technology via EMMA will add further value to such a new service. The next steps would be to formulate a business plan for a precision mouse model service by incorporating the experiences from this pilot service.

Application Form

INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

INFRAFRONTIER2020 Project - Trans-national Access call

January 2019

Precision mammalian model development / mouse

Call information and application form

Context and aims of the call

INFRAFRONTIER is the European Research Infrastructure for phenotyping and archiving of model mammalian genomes. The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure provides access to first-class tools and data for biomedical research, and thereby contributes to improving the understanding of gene function in human health and disease using the mouse model. The core services of INFRAFRONTIER comprise the systemic phenotyping of mouse mutants in the participating mouse clinics, and the archiving and distribution of mouse mutant lines by the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA).

Main objective of this INFRAFRONTIER open call is to facilitate access for the wider biomedical research community to the unique infrastructure and scientific expertise of the participating INFRAFRONTIER partners, to deliver novel mouse lines that will advance knowledge of human disease and will be of widespread use in biomedical science. Recent advances in genome editing technology will be used to develop new mouse models of human disease. INFRAFRONTIER will provide open access to all newly developed disease models through the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA). Access to this free-of-charge-service will be granted on the basis of the applicant's research plans and the potential impact of the proposed novel mouse line on the wider biomedical research community.

This Trans-national Access call of the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project supports a total of 12 precision mouse model development projects. A complementary call provides support for 3 customised rat model development projects.

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project has received funding from the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. Developing new world class research infrastructures)

Trans-national Access (TA) activity of the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project Free of charge precision mammalian model development service / Access modalities

- The EC Horizon 2020 funded INFRAFRONTIER2020 project (2017 – 2020) supports eligible customers with a free-of-charge mouse model development service implemented as a Trans-national Access activity supporting a total of 12 projects in this call.
- The **access unit** offered covers the production of a single F1 genome-edited mouse line (at least one individual of a F1 genome edited mouse line will be provided).
- The **model development service** involves project design including prediction of off-target sites, preparation of sgRNA's and Cas9 mRNA/protein, and injection into zygotes to generate F0 founder mutant animals (C57BL/6N or C57BL/6J genetic background preferred). Selected F0 animals will be bred to germ line to produce F1 genome edited animals. **Possible allele types that can be generated are indels, exon deletions (< 10kb) and point mutation insertions.** Newly developed mouse models will be made available to selected applicants within an average of 12 months following provision of all required information to start the mouse production.
- The generated **mouse models will be made available to the scientific community.** An optional grace period of up to 1 year for mouse resources may apply, with immediate release of mouse resources after expiry of the grace period. Mouse mutant lines will be deposited into the INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA repository for subsequent use by the scientific community. Newly developed mouse models will be owned by the production centres and will be distributed by the INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA repository using their institutional MTAs.
- **Costs:** The access to the INFRAFRONTIER2020 model development service is free of charge. However, the shipment cost of the newly developed mouse models must be borne by the applicants.
- **Eligibility:** The INFRAFRONTIER2020 **Trans-national Access call is open** and proposals can be submitted from applicants around the world. Ten projects must be allocated to applicants from EU Member States and Associated Countries, and two projects can be allocated to applicants from third countries.
- **Application:** Service requests for the INFRAFRONTIER2020 model development service can be made via this **application form**. Applications for the Trans-national Access activity must include a short description of the research plans for utilising the newly developed mouse model that is being generated by the INFRAFRONTIER2020 TA service.
- **Selection procedure:** Proposals from eligible customers for free of charge access to the INFRAFRONTIER2020 mouse model development service will be subject to a review procedure. The review will be based on short descriptions of the projects involving the mouse mutants that will be produced by the TA service. A mixed panel

of members of INFRAFRONTIER and of an external Evaluation Committee will assess service requests supported by the TA activity. In addition to scientific merit of applicants, soundness of the proposal and research plans, the beneficial impact of the proposed novel mouse line on the wider biomedical research community will be assessed. Applicants will be informed on the outcome of the evaluation within 6 weeks after the end of the call for which the TA application was submitted. All applications will be handled with strict confidentiality.

- **Acknowledgements:** Please do acknowledge any support under this scheme in all resulting publications with "Part of this work has been funded by the European Union Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (Grant Agreement Number 730879). The participating infrastructure which provided the service should be specifically mentioned in any publication resulting from the service.

Support offered

Beyond the TA service provision applicants will benefit from extensive user support which covers detailed consulting on project design. Gene-editing approaches frequently yield a number of mutant alleles which can be provided and cryopreserved (at additional cost) for later use as only selected founder animals will be bred to the F1 generation. Logistic support will be provided by arranging shipments to the applicant's animal facilities. At additional cost a colony expansion can be provided. For long term availability new animal models will be cryopreserved by the participating production centres at own cost and deposited into the EMMA repository under standard conditions (<https://www.infrafrontier.eu/resources-and-services/deposit-mice-emma-repository>).

The participating INFRAFRONTIER partners routinely provide mouse model development services using all standard approaches such as gene targeting, the generation of chimeric mice from gene-targeted ES cells and gene editing technologies such as TALENs or CRISPR/Cas9. Participating centres like the Sanger Institute are engaged in large scale in house production projects and have a capacity of 100 to 150 model development projects per year. Partners operating transgenic service platforms routinely provide model development services to academic clients from across the world.

Participating infrastructures:

- Biological Sciences Research Centre A. Fleming (Fleming)
- Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC-CNB)
- Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI)
- Genome Research Limited (Sanger Institute)

**Application Form - INFRAFRONTIER2020 precision mammalian model development
Closing of call on February 15th - Evaluation process until March 15th**

First name	
Family name	
Email	
Phone	
Fax	
Institution	
Address	
Town	
Postcode	
Country	
Link to lab website	
Link to publication list	

**The following data is required by the EC for statistical purposes.
Applications can only be considered if all data are provided.**

Gender	
Birth year	
Nationality	
Researcher status (e.g. Prof, Postdoc)	
Scientific background	

I have read, understood and agree to the [INFRAFRONTIER data privacy policy](#)

Description of proposed project

Please describe briefly the proposed project involving the mouse mutant line to be developed using genome editing technology. This proposal will be the foundation for the evaluation of your project. Informal enquiries prior to proposal submission are welcome via proposals@infrafrontier.eu

Gene of interest	

Please, do not extend beyond the provided space (max 2 pages including references).

Send your proposal to proposals@infrafrontier.eu by February 15th 2019.

INFRAFRONTIER2020 project description

INFRAFRONTIER2020 - Towards enduring mouse resources and services advancing research into human health and disease

INFRAFRONTIER2020 objectives

The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure integrates European Mouse Clinics and the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA) with the common goal to ensure access to mouse models for basic research of human health and disease, and to translate this knowledge into therapeutic approaches for the benefit of the European society.

The expanded INFRAFRONTIER2020 network, coordinated by the INFRAFRONTIER GmbH, includes 3 SMEs and is strategically responding to the INFRADEV3 call with aligned objectives to advance the long-term sustainability which are **1)** development of business models and a stable legal framework; **2)** raise awareness of the INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure; **3)** provide bespoke services aligned with user demands; **4)** promote best practices in mouse phenogenomics; **5)** enhance robustness of the INFRAFRONTIER IT infrastructure and use of the EMMA strain resource; and **6)** improve business processes. Towards achieving these objectives key INFRAFRONTIER2020 project deliverables are:

- INFRAFRONTIER Business Plan2.0, and business models for all services
- Stable legal framework built on the INFRAFRONTIER legal entity
- INFRAFRONTIER annual stakeholder conferences
- Customised mouse model and secondary phenotyping pilot services
- INFRAFRONTIER advanced training schools in mouse phenogenomics
- Reengineered EMMA Database2.0 system
- Annotated mouse models of human diseases
- Quality management system for the legal entity

INFRAFRONTIER2020 will **1)** enhance the sustainable operation of the INFRAFRONTIER RI; **2)** continue to structure the ERA, **3)** foster innovation, and **4)** address major societal challenges in human health by customised service pilots supporting research into common and rare diseases. A sustainable INFRAFRONTIER RI will ensure the quality of deposited mice and support the reproducibility of biological results. Outreach efforts will raise awareness of resources and services and facilitate sustainable engagement with industry and global consortia such as the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project has received funding from the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. Developing new world class research infrastructures)

